

Milestone: M3.3 List of best practices in sharing and linking phenotypic and genetic data

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Means of Verification

B1MG google doc environment:

[Best_practices_set_up_working_document_v1.x - Google Documenten](#)

As well as official released versions on [Zenodo](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No, list of best practices is available and continuously updated

This list is an integrated item of D3.7 and D3.8. D3.7 however has been rejected and is currently being revised. Whether to be published as D3.7 v2 or directly as D3.8 is being discussed with PO

Project participants & others

See contributing authors in

[Best_practices_set_up_working_document_v1.x - Google Documenten](#) and the Zenodo publication(s)

Next action steps

List of best and promising practices is available and continuously updated

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